

Should labeling be enforced on genetically designed products ?

H.K. GARG

GOVERNMENT MOTILAL VIGYAN MAHAVIDYALAYA
BHOPAL - 462008 (INDIA)
drharikrishnagarg@gmail.com

JAYA GARG

ORIENTAL INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY
BHOPAL - 462021 (INDIA)
hjkkrish@gmail.com

The use of genetically designed organisms has sparked significant controversy in many areas. Some groups or individuals see the generation and use of GMO as intolerable meddling with biological states or processes that have naturally evolved over long periods of time, while others are concerned about the limitations of modern science to fully comprehend all of the potential negative ramifications of genetic manipulation.

Labeling legislation has been introduced and rejected several times since 1996 on the grounds of 'restraint of trade' due to the cost of labeling. The controversy erupted again in 2009 when Graincorp, the U.S. largest grain handler, announced it would mix GM Canola with its unmodified grain. Traditional growers, who largely rely on GM-free markets, had been told that they would have to pay huge money to get endorsement on their products as GM free.

Outside the U.S., the entire European Union and other countries such as Australia, China, Japan, and Russia require GMO labeling. In Australia, multiple surveys have shown that while 45% of the public accept GM foods, some 93% demand all genetically modified foods be labeled as such. In 2007, a survey by the Food Standards Australia and New Zealand depicted that 27% of Australians looked at the label to see if it contained GM material. There are other countries that make GMO labeling voluntary and many other countries have plans to introduce GMO labeling.

In May 2012, the U.S. State of California voted on the labeling of genetically modified food. They opined that consumers have a right to know the content of their food and have a choice to avoid it if they do not wish to eat. On the other hand, advocates such as Du Pont, Monsanto and the Council for Biotechnology Information, which represents agribusiness, call it an attempt to scare consumers and make them feel that the food is unsafe. Though Biotechnology labeling is not enforced by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), yet it has been adopted by over 40 countries. The present report summarizes an all-inclusive account of the virtues of labeling GMO products.

Key words : GMO, Genetically designed food, Labeling of GM products.

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